

DENIS PETRINA¹

MACHINA SAPIENS

Artificial Intelligence Between the Symptomatics of Cognitive Capitalism and the Revolutionary Promise of Posthumanism

ABSTRACT

This paper situates Artificial Intelligence (AI) within two conflicting theoretical frameworks—cognitive capitalism and posthumanism—to explore its dual role as both a symptom of capitalist exploitation and a distinct cognizing agent that necessitates posthumanist analysis. The first section examines AI's evolution as *machina sapiens* in the problematic context of the Marxist notion of the general intellect, tracing its development through the interplay of cybernetics, ICT, and the planetary-scale megastructure of cognitive capitalism (the Stack). Drawing on Benjamin Bratton's insights, it argues that cognitive capitalism embeds AI within exploitative frameworks of reification of information and knowledge commodification. The second section adopts posthumanist perspectives to challenge binary distinctions between humans and machines. Engaging with hypernaturalist theories and Katherine Hayles' concept of cognitive assemblages, it reconceptualizes agency as

collective, material, and entangled, moving beyond humanist assumptions about intelligence and cognition. In its conclusion, the paper introduces *nooecological noopolitics* as a paradigm to navigate the tensions between the exploitative dynamics of cognitive capitalism and AI's transformative potential. This vision imagines a future where cognition, knowledge, and agency are reconfigured within a hybrid, symbiotic, and generative commons.

KEYWORDS: cognitive capitalism, post-Marxist theory of AI, posthumanism, hypernaturalism, AGI (Artificial General Intelligence), GAI (General Artificial Intelligence)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: Funding provided by the Lithuanian Research Council, Postdoctoral Research Project "New Media Materialism: Posthumanist Perspective". Contract No P-PD-26-062 (Institution: European Humanities University).

¹ Denis Petrina (he/him) is a Researcher at the Lithuanian Culture Research Institute (Department of Contemporary Philosophy) and a Scientific Fellow at European Humanities University (Vilnius, Lithuania). He has successfully defended his doctoral dissertation on philosophical interpretations and biopolitical implications of the notion of affect (Vilnius, Lithuania, 2022). His research interests include new (media) materialism, posthumanism and posthumanities, quantum metaphysics, affect theory, and queer studies.

INTRODUCTION: THE CONCEPTUAL-PROBLEMATIC ANATOMY OF *MACHINA SAPIENS*

The increasingly widespread adoption of Artificial Intelligence technologies—such as Large Language Models (LLMs, most prominently exemplified by ChatGPT), AI-powered robotics, and generative creative tools like DALL-E or MidJourney—marks not only a tectonic shift in technology development, but also an existential and ontological rupture. Stuart Russell and Peter Norvig define AI as a collective class of intelligent agents capable of natural language processing, knowledge representation, automated reasoning, and machine learning.² Unlike traditional automation, which supplanted *manual labor*, these systems infiltrate the domain of human thought itself, redefining intelligence, creativity, and communication—core tenets of contemporary immaterial capitalism, as Michael Hardt and Antonio Negri argue.³ More significantly, these technologies herald a novel iteration of cognitive automation: *adaptive* systems that learn from data and engage in *abductive* reasoning, which distinguishes them from earlier systems rooted in either *deductive* or *inductive* logic.⁴

The breathtaking scale of the effects of these technologies has elicited polarized responses, from enthusiastic celebration of their seemingly boundless potential to deep anxieties about their prospect to considerably surpass human cognitive capacities. These responses are symptomatic of what Siegfried Zielinski calls *psychopathia medialis*^{5,6}—the unresolved tension between “the social and political macrocosm” and “the microcosm of the individual brain”⁷ caused by the very process of mediation. Jeffrey Sconce, in *Haunted Media*, delves deeper into this psychopathology of media, interpreting the “psychopathic” not merely as a metaphor, but rather as a tangible potential for mass hysteria and collective paranoia. From séances, telepathy, and automatic writing⁸ to clinical cases of psychosis caused by so-called “influencing machines,” Sconce identifies a historical continuum in which media technologies evoke “the electrifyingly impalpable threat of invisible mental power” to human well-being.⁹

As AI increasingly mimics and even transcends human cognitive functions, it is this *impalpable threat of the mental power of the machine* that appears unsettling. AI challenges not only the boundaries of individual’s body or brain but further extends into

² Stuart Russell and Peter Norvig, *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach* (New Jersey: Pearson Education, 2003), 2-3.

³ Michael Hardt and Antonio Negri, *Empire* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2000), 402.

⁴ Luciana Parisi, “Critical Computation: Digital Automata and General Artificial Thinking,” *Theory, Culture & Society* 36, no. 2 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276418818889>.

⁵ Siegfried Zielinski, *Deep Time of the Media: Toward an Archeology of Hearing and Seeing by Technical Means* (Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2006), 8.

⁶ Jussi Parikka establishes a correlation between *psychopathia medialis* and the capitalist teleology of technology. Parikka 2012, 12.

⁷ Siegfried Zielinski, “Against Psychopathia Medialis—For Normal Schizophrenia,” *In/Compatible Research* 1, no. 2 (2012): 8, <https://aprja.net/issue/view/8373/862>.

⁸ Jeffrey Sconce, *Haunted Media: Electronic Presence from Telegraphy to Television* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2000), 24.

⁹ Jeffrey Sconce, *The Technical Delusion: Electronics, Power, Insanity* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2019), 174.

the realm of *ontobiology*. Can we call ourselves *homo sapiens*, when the defining feature of our species—*sapiens*—is now outsourced to intelligent machines that often outperform humans in cognitive tasks? Yet, Darwin’s acknowledgment of the “undiscovered and undiscoverable essence of the term species” invites reconsideration: is this so-called “psychotic” loss of the human self as alarming as it seems?¹⁰

Materialist media and technology theory—rooted in new materialism, object- and process-oriented ontologies, and posthumanism—offers a contrasting perspective. Rather than preserving the ephemeral human within the intricate and complex network of *biodigital technosomatic* interfaces, these theoretical frameworks emphasize the processual, material-discursive construction of the human. This shift marks a decisive break from the so-called *representational media paradigms*, which center on semiotics (signification) and axiomatics (moral implications) in mediated processes of representation, aiming to re/construct reality through symbols, images, and narratives. In contrast, *materialist media theory* focuses on the “materialities of relations and sensations”¹¹ intrinsic to mediation, aligning with Katherine Hayles’ notion of “technogenesis”: a co-evolutionary process in which humans and technologies undergo “coordinated transformations.”¹²

However, these transformations do not unfold in a vacuum. The unsettling nature of these chimeric couplings between human and machine—what Hayles terms “cognitive assemblages”—stems not from their perceived “paranormal” qualities, but from their deep entrenchment within the broader (infra)structure of *cognitive capitalism*.¹³ As Yann Moulier-Boutang explains, this emerging power constellation “has to deal with collective cognitive labour power, living labour, and no longer simply with muscle-power consumed by machines driven by ‘fossil-fuel’ energy.”¹⁴ Within this constellation, intelligence—both human and non-human—becomes a primary site of capital accumulation, as well as a resource for extraction and commodification.

This paper critiques AI—and its prospective extension into Artificial General Intelligence (AGI)—within the symptomatology of cognitive capitalism, framing it alongside another critical notion in contemporary autonomist Marxist critiques: the *general intellect*. Paolo Virno succinctly describes the problematics of the general intellect as “the knowledge objectified in fixed capital and embodied or enmeshed in the automated system of machinery.”¹⁵ I therefore argue that within cognitive capitalism, AI functions both as a repository of collective knowledge and a material manifestation

¹⁰ Charles Darwin, “On the Origin of Species by Means of Natural Selection (1859),” in *Evolutionary Writings*, ed. James Secord (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008), 207.

¹¹ Parikka Jussi, “New Materialism as Media Theory: Medianatures and Dirty Matter,” *Communication and Critical/Cultural Studies* 9, no.1(2012): 96.

¹² Katherine Hayles, *How We Think: Digital Media and Contemporary Technogenesis* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2012), 81.

¹³ Katherine Hayles, *Unthought: The Power of the Cognitive Nonconscious* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2017), 116.

¹⁴ Yann Moulier-Boutang, *Cognitive Capitalism*, trans. Ed Emery (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2011), 37.

¹⁵ Paolo Virno, “General Intellect,” *Historical Materialism* 15, no.3(2007): 3.

of the general intellect, commodifying the foundational processes of cognition and communication that define humanity. In doing so, it reconfigures the role of knowledge and cognitive labor in capital production through revolutionary forms and unprecedented scales of adaptive automation. Situating AI within the framework of the general intellect underscores its dual nature: both as a tool for capital extraction and a potential for reimagining human-machine entanglements beyond Mark Fisher’s disheartening hypothesis of “capitalist realism.”¹⁶ Thus, in the second part, it advocates for ontopolitical paradigms that transcend humanity not merely technically, but also epistemologically, ontologically, and ethically. Ultimately, the paper introduces a conceptual framework—*nooecological noopolitics*—to envision these paradigms and outline the contours of a potential posthuman emancipatory horizon.

THE GENESIS OF *MACHINA SAPIENS* IN COGNITIVE CAPITALISM: FROM CYBERNETICS TO THE STACK

In his seminal study *Cybernetics: On Control and Communication in the Animal and the Machine* (1948), the father of cybernetics, Norbert Wiener, traces the genealogy of the automaton within the dynamic context of scientific developments. Using technological metaphors—such as the clockwork of the eighteenth century, the steam engine of the nineteenth century, and ultimately the technologies of communication and control of the twentieth century—he illustrates how technological epistemes have shaped both the social imaginary and the socioeconomic configurations across different historical periods.¹⁷ Crucially, Wiener’s vision of cybernetics as a feedback-driven system of communication and control serves as a precursor to AI systems, which thrive on iterative learning, real-time data processing, and adaptive behavior.

Building on this lineage, Gilles Deleuze in his “Postscript on the Societies of Control” operationalizes the metaphor of the machine. However, unlike Wiener, he views these technological shifts not as mere iconography of their respective eras but as the *diagrammatics of power*, symptomatic of the evolving forms of capitalist society.¹⁸ Drawing heavily on Foucault, Deleuze argues that the transition from the clockwork to the steam engine represents both a quantitative and qualitative shift—from a capitalism rooted in discipline, precision, regime, and mechanical efficiency to one centered around productivity, industrialization, and large-scale machine production. The ensuing *cybernetic* century, as Deleuze contends, marked a new era of capitalism, associated with “free-floating control” implemented through computers as a means of “a universal modulation”—dynamic, fluid, and pervasive *modus operandi* of power facilitated

¹⁶ Mark Fisher, *Capitalist Realism: Is There No Alternative?* (Winchester: Zero Books, 2009).

¹⁷ Norbert Wiener, *Cybernetics, or Control and Communication in the Animal and the Machine* (Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2019), 57.

¹⁸ Gilles Deleuze, “Postscript on the Societies of Control,” *October* 59 (1992). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/778828>.

by real-time feedback and continuous adjustments.¹⁹ This concept of modulation prefigures the role of adaptive AI within the novel capitalist configuration, exemplifying this logic by processing feedback to optimize performance and embedding modulation at the core of both production and governance, as will be further demonstrated.

In his *Grundrisse*, particularly in “The Fragment on Machines,” Karl Marx introduces the crucial notion of the *general intellect*, which serves as a theoretical foundation for understanding this evolution. For Marx, the general intellect represents the fusion of collective knowledge and technological capacity within society, a force that becomes decisive under conditions of automation.²⁰ Building upon Marx, Michael Hardt and Antonio Negri define the general intellect as “a collective, social intelligence created by accumulated knowledges, techniques, and know-how.”²¹ In the cybernetic century, this concept gains renewed relevance as machines—most notably exemplified by AI—operate adaptively and autonomously through incessant modulation, epitomizing the interplay of human and machine intelligence that were envisioned by Wiener and depicted by Deleuze.

Modulation, therefore, far from being a technological phenomenon bridging cybernetics and control, emerges as the defining logic of *cognitive capitalism*. Through the integration of human labor with adaptive automated systems, modulation functions as a hybrid force that commodifies the cognitive and communicative capacities of the general intellect. A distinctive feature of cognitive capitalism is thus its increasing reliance on the seamless synthesis of human and machinic contributions. This dynamic is aptly captured by Carlo Vercellone and Alfonso Giuliani, who, in the introduction to the volume dedicated to cognitive capitalism, write:

The fields of artificial intelligence, biotechnologies, nanotechnologies, the construction of human tissues with genetic experimentation, neurosciences, the industry of processing masses of increasingly complex and individualized data (big data), show a distinct process in which the becoming-human of the machine is combined with the becoming-machine of the human.²²

The described dynamic aligns with the broader framework of Autonomist Marxist tradition, which critically reexamines the mutually determined relationship between labor, value, and technology in cognitive capitalism. As its descriptor suggests, cognitive capitalism thrives on mental, intellectual and creative labor, positioning information as the key currency of this new economic system. The conceptual intersection of information and value traces its roots to earlier efforts to integrate cybernetics

¹⁹ Deleuze, 4, 7.

²⁰ Karl Marx, *Grundrisse: Foundations of the Critique of Political Economy*, trans. Martin Nicolaus (New York: Vintage Books, 1973), 607.

²¹ Michael Hardt and Antonio Negri, *Empire* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2000), 364.

²² Carlo Vercellone and Alfonso Giuliani, “An introduction to cognitive capitalism: A Marxist approach,” in *Cognitive Capitalism, Welfare and Labor: The Commonfare Hypothesis*, ed. Andrea Fumagalli, Alfonso Giuliani, Stefano Lucarelli, and Carlo Vercellone (London and New York: Routledge, 2019), 3.

into Marxist critique. Among the pioneering attempts to address the problem of cognitive capitalism in relation to cybernetics was the work of Italian Autonomist Marxist Romano Alquati. Alquati highlighted the conceptual continuity between the notions of *information* in cybernetics and *value* in Marxist theory through his concept of *informational surplus value*. Referring to Alquati's insights as the *avant la lettre* postulate of cognitive capitalism, Pasquinelli quotes: "Productive labour is defined by the quality of information elaborated and transmitted by worker to the means of production via the mediation of constant capital."²³ Further, Pasquinelli situates Alquati's insights within the context of the automation of control:

In fact, the important insight advanced by Alquati is the continuum merging bureaucracy, cybernetics and machinery: cybernetics unveils the machinic nature of bureaucracy and conversely the 'bureaucratic' role of machines, as they are feedback apparatuses that control workers and capture their know-how of the production. Valorising information is then what enters the cybernetic machine and it is transformed into a sort of machinic knowledge.²⁴

The *valorization of information through the production of machinic knowledge* defines cognitive capitalism in the age of cybernetics, and acts as the main driver of *surplus informational value*. AI systems, particularly generative AI models such as ChatGPT or DALL-E, exemplify this process by employing iterative learning processes to produce outputs—texts, images, codes—that are immediately commodifiable and can be fed into platforms, enterprises, or entire markets that capitalize on their scalability. By generating vast amounts of new information—and, consequently, surplus informational value—from existing datasets, these systems transform raw data into a primary site of value production and extraction. These and other AI-augmented value chains, driven by their adaptive capabilities, significantly enhance machinic knowledge by embedding generative capacities into workflows and enabling continuous cycles of data generation, refinement, and valorization. This *machinic* cognitive labor, preying on *human* cognitive labor, contributes to and accelerates the "reification of information" and the commodification of knowledge—both foundational pillars of cognitive capitalism in the cybernetic age.²⁵

²³ Romano Alquati, "Composizione organica del capitale e forza-lavoro alla Olivetti," *Quaderni Rossi*, no. 2-3 (1962-1963), <https://www.bibliotecaginobianco.it/flip/QUIR/002/02/#98>, quoted in Matteo Pasquinelli, "Machinic Capitalism and Network Surplus Value: Notes on the Political Economy of the Turing Machine," (presentation, Joy Forever: Political Economy of Social Creativity Conference, Warsaw, October 20-22, 2011), *Lust for Life*, accessed September 7, 2024. https://lust-for-life.org/Lust-For-Life/_Textual/MatteoPasquinelli_MachinicCapitalismAndNetworkSurplusValue-NotesOnThePoliticalEconomyOfTheTuringMachine_2011_28pp/MatteoPasquinelli_MachinicCapitalismAndNetworkSurplusValue-NotesOnThePoliticalEconomyOfTheTuringMachine_2011_28pp.pdf

²⁴ Pasquinelli, "Machinic Capitalism and Network Surplus Value."

²⁵ Katherine Hayles, *How We Became Posthuman: Virtual Bodies in Cybernetics, Literature, and Informatics* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1999), 50.

Within this problematic configuration, under the conditions of cognitive capitalism, AI functions as a double agent: it *commodifies* cognitive labor simultaneously existing as a *commodified* form of the general intellect. In this context, the current trajectory toward the development of Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), often regarded as the ultimate instantiation of the cybernetic general intellect, appears particularly ominous. As Jeff Clune validly argues, AGI represents “a grand new challenge of the computer research”—a designation that also marks a new horizon for cybernetic cognitive capitalism.²⁶ At its core, AGI represents the aspiration to instantiate a more comprehensive cybernetic general intellect, holding the promise of encompassing—and potentially surpassing—the full spectrum of human cognitive labor. Its potential to transcend task-specific capabilities and operate autonomously across diverse domains signals an unprecedented convergence of human and machinic labor, hypostasized in a single cognizing entity. This convergence, however, leads to an unexpected conclusion: the dichotomy between the human’s and the machine’s intellectual labor, which fuels what Bassett and Roberts term “automation anxiety,” becomes increasingly irrelevant.²⁷ Both human and artificial intelligence—envisioned to ultimately converge in AGI—risk being subsumed under the logic, axiomatics, and pragmatics of cognitive capitalism.

The emergence of AI as an autonomous intelligent agent—that is, operating independently of direct human intervention, enabled by machine learning algorithms and neural networks—vividly illustrates the extension of the general intellect, understood as collectively shared knowledge, into the machinic domain. Within this extension, machinic knowledge, generated through the reification of information and the convergence of human and machinic labor, drives the production of informational surplus value. Under the conditions of cognitive and/or cybernetic capitalism, this process operates through modulation, which, as Deleuze explains, embodies adaptive, fluid, and dynamic—yet pervasive—control mechanisms that perpetually extract value.

Benjamin Bratton’s concept of *the Stack* captures the dynamics of such modulation *qua* control, portraying a planetary-scale computational infrastructure built upon interconnected layers, each defined by modularity and the circulation of information across technical and institutional domains.²⁸ This layered structure replaces the Westphalian logic of sovereignty with a new *nomos* of global information networks characterized by decentralization, automation, and incessant information flows. In a creative coupling of geopolitics and design, Bratton persuasively illustrates the redefinition of governance as distributed power across the layers of the Stack in an increasingly interconnected and informationally governed—essentially, entangled—world. The

²⁶ Jeff Clune, “AI-GAs: AI-generating algorithms, an alternate paradigm for producing general artificial intelligence,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.10985*, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1905.10985>.

²⁷ Caroline Bassett and Ben Roberts, “Automation Now and Then: Automation Fevers, Anxieties, and Utopias,” *New Formations: A Journal of Culture/Theory/Politics* 98 (2020): 9–28, <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/747018>.

²⁸ Benjamin Bratton, *The Stack: On Software and Sovereignty* (Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2015), 44.

modular architecture of the Stack exemplifies the pervasive modulation of human and machinic agency in the production, governance, and appropriation of surplus informational value. AI plays an increasingly pivotal role in facilitating the entangled dynamics of the Stack: each layer of the Stack functions distinctly yet all levels function interdependently, with AI, as a critical agent, enhancing their integration and operational efficiency.

For instance, the Earth layer situates computation within the material domain, and in doing so transforms the planet into a site of data-driven geoengineering. AI-powered systems, deployed in global climate and weather modeling, analyze vast environmental datasets to optimize predictive models and facilitate interventions, such as energy distribution or disaster management.²⁹

Above it, the Cloud layer functions as the infosphere of the Stack, encompassing the vast infrastructural complex that includes “server farms, massive databases, energy sources, optical cables, wireless transmission media, and distributed applications.”³⁰ Generative AI models like ChatGPT or DALL-E operate within this layer, processing immense datasets stored in the Cloud to produce commodifiable outputs. Described as “cosmically inflated ontological computationalism,” this layer vividly illustrates the Deleuzian logic of immanent control by perpetually generating, adapting, and optimizing information flows.³¹

The *Address* layer mediates between the *Cloud* and the *City*. Through IP addresses, geolocation, indexing protocols, and other means of identification, it facilitates transactions and connections across these domains. Augmented by AI, it achieves precise location tracking, real-time data synchronization, and predictive analytics, ensuring seamless connectivity between digital and physical infrastructures. In the *City* layer, which represents the operational *locus* of cognitive capitalism, AI-powered systems optimize urban life from energy consumption and traffic management to comprehensive urban planning, embedding machinic cognition into the very fabric of metropolitan environments.

The *Interface* layer bridges the *User* and the Stack in a dynamic feedback loop. As a sensory-visual gateway, it allows the *User* to access the totality of the Stack while simultaneously enabling the Stack to harvest data from the *User*.³² Described by Bratton not as merely the sensory-visual technology, but as a “cosmogram,”³³ this multimedia construct synthesizes technical affordances of the Stack “through which local signification and significance are programmed.”³⁴ It therefore significantly shapes the semiotics and semantics of mediated systems in which we are inescapably immersed. For example, AI-driven capabilities, such as real-time interactions, sentiment analysis, and

²⁹ Bratton, 76.

³⁰ Bratton, 70.

³¹ Bratton, 417.

³² Bratton, 297.

³³ Bratton, 243.

³⁴ Bratton, 71.

adaptive personalization not only tailor the experience to individual but also, more importantly, perpetuate an endless cycle of machinic knowledge expansion and value extraction through data collection.

Ultimately, the *User* layer highlights the fragmentation of the political subject into various quantified and datafied forms—what Deleuze refers to as *dividuals*. Bratton delineates Human User, Animal User, AI User, and Machine User as distinct forms of data subjects.³⁵ Rather than defined by substantialist agency, the User emerges as a situational construct shaped by intersecting flows of information. Its appearance in the political horizon signals the eclipse of political humanism, as the hybrid production of surplus informational value blurs the boundaries between human and machinic cognitive labor.³⁶ Obviously, AI facilitates and amplifies these dynamics.

The significance of AI within the cosmic configuration of the Stack signals a tectonic shift toward automation and systemic self-sufficiency. Acting as the connective tissue binding the Stack's layers, AI leverages its cognitive capacities—spanning prognostics, prediction, data analysis, real-time adaptability and optimization—to ensure and enhance the seamless flow of information across interconnected layers. Its capability to process immense datasets, derive actionable insights, and continuously refine itself underscores its dual role in cognitive capitalism: both as a generative engine of machinic knowledge and as driving force in the reification of information and extraction of informational surplus value. However, its unprecedented efficiency comes at a steep ecological cost, as the material foundations of the Stack reveal deeper entanglements with planetary limits.

Therefore, in addition to his thorough analysis of the capitalist dynamics of the Stack, Bratton situates it within a broader theoretical framework of the Anthropocene—an era in which human activity becomes a dominant geological force, exceeding human control and threatening the collapse of ecosystems at all scales, including those created by humans. As aptly noted by Bratton, the seemingly immaterial planetary megastructure of the Stack requires colossal material resources—carbon and fossil fuels, silicon, rare earth metals, etc.—to be sustained.³⁷ Given the scale and ongoing expansion of the Stack and AI systems, this designates a dramatic trajectory toward eventual depletion and subsequent absolute exhaustion of these finite natural resources. This poses a challenge both for the planet and the Stack, which of course, offers little chance of reconciliation, as the very forces that threaten the Stack also endanger the planet. Thus, Parikka, when discussing the Anthropocene, refers to it as the *anthrobscene*, highlighting “the unsustainable, politically dubious, and ethically suspicious practices that maintain technological culture and its corporate networks.”³⁸ Alongside these frames of reference, AI as the novel, active and integral agent of contemporary cognitive capitalism amplifies these exploitative practices and accelerates ecological

³⁵ Bratton, 274-84.

³⁶ Bratton, 361.

³⁷ Bratton, 303.

³⁸ Jussi Parikka, *The Anthrobscene* (Minneapolis: The University of Minnesota Press, 2014), 26.

degradation, being enmeshed in the networks it sustains.

Ultimately, Luciana Parisi articulates a frequently overlooked dark side of immaterial capitalism—its deep entanglement with the exploitative system of patriarchy. Here, AI embodies what Parisi refers to as “the phantasmaphysics” of disembodiment, which is symptomatic of the patriarchal ontoepistemology that privileges the “metaphysics of representation” over *incorporeal materialism*.^{39,40} This essentially dichotomic Cartesian project, with its grotesque “mind over matter” principle, exemplifies the dialectical framework of Western epistemology, which Parisi links to the patriarchal dream of disembodiment—of total subjugation of matter to mind. Parisi identifies this ideal as “the ultimate triumph of the patriarchal model of pleasure, a longing for disembodiment and self-satisfaction.”⁴¹

If conceptualized as an evolutionary stage—or, rather, an intense culmination—of cognitive capitalism, AI embodies the cognitive element of the mind/matter equation, *cogito*, mirroring Cartesian *cogito ergo sum* and enshrining the primacy of sterile rational agency. In doing so, AI epitomizes the phallogocentric aspiration for the absolute dominance of reason over materiality. As such, AI can be viewed as a profound ideological manifestation of Cartesian and patriarchal legacies. It is, however, more productive to shift the focus from the cognitive to the material—or, more precisely, the *hypermaterial*—where the very ontology disrupts the boundaries between *homo*, *cogito*, *machina*, and *natura*.

THE TECHNOGENESIS OF *HOMO* AND *MACHINA SAPIENS*: HYPERNATURALIST PERSPECTIVE

A focal point of various materialist critiques—Marxist, feminist, posthumanist, and others—is the concept of matter as inherently agential. It conceptually and ethically opposes classical representational Western ontology, where matter was regarded as equivalent to the principle of passivity or inertia, contraposed to active and rational agency. Cognitive capitalism perpetuates this framing through its instrumentalist logic, treating matter and information as substrates for the extraction of surplus value. Materialist critiques, however, expose matter as an active *ontogenetic* force—not merely a means to an end but one that shapes and conditions our entangled material existence.

³⁹ Luciana Parisi, *Abstract Sex: Philosophy, Biotechnology, and the Mutations of Desire* (London and New York: Continuum, 2004), 160-61.

⁴⁰ For further elaboration, see Luce Irigaray’s illuminating essay, “Mechanics of Fluids,” where she addresses the persistent problem in Western ontoepistemology of the mind vs. matter dualism through the lens of the mechanics of solids and fluids. Irigaray extensively argues that the Phallus establishes a persistent “teleology of reabsorption of fluid in a solidified form.” In Platonic terms, this teleology is rooted in the subjugation of *hyle* (matter) to *eidos* (form), essentially – mind (solid) over matter (fluid). Luce Irigaray, *This Sex Which Is Not One*, trans. Catherine Porter and Carolyn Burke (New York: Cornell University Press, 1985), 110.

⁴¹ Parisi, 12.

Parisi therefore outlines “an alternative metaphysics of matter,”⁴² essentially Spinozian *natura naturans*, the naturing nature, introducing her intriguing concept of hypernature.⁴³ In a provocative conceptual move, Parisi contends that hypernature preemptively claims the cessation of “the battle between extension and intensity, cause and effects, mind and body, god and things”—the binaries representational ontologies rest upon. Instead, hypernature emerges as “the composition of free intensities, molecular populations of flows that are autonomous yet coexistent with the processes of organization of matter constituting the biophysical, biocultural, and biodigital strata.”⁴⁴ This reconfiguration toward the agency of nature marks not only an onto *epistemological* departure from the dichotomy of *mind* vs. *matter* but a profound onto *existential* shift, inextricably intertwining *homo* and *machina*, biology and technology.

As Parisi eloquently explains, “the biodigital reconfiguration of the body partakes on a hypernatural plane, where particles, not parts, recombine, where forces, and not categories, clash.”⁴⁵ Conventionally juxtaposed against culture and digitality, nature and matter—or *hypernature*—operate through the power of ontological difference, where fixed and static entities give way to immanent becomings that defy the demarcation between biology and technology, emerging instead from their intricate entanglement. In this sense, through “disjunctive synthesis”—being *together/apart*, they converge into an all-encompassing continuum.⁴⁶

This configuration, however, presents a significant theoretical challenge, as hypernature both encompasses and extends the megastructure of the Stack, the foundational pillar of cognitive capitalism. As posited by the theory of the Capitalocene,⁴⁷ there exists “the hypermaterialist field of Kapital,” which is best encapsulated in Timothy Morton’s notion of *hyperobject*.⁴⁸ A hyperobject is a real material force that, in its vast scale, surpasses human comprehension yet exerts an utterly tangible and oftentimes destructive effect on human and non-human ecologies. Morton argues that capital as a hyperobject objectifies and commodifies other hyperobjects, such as the biosphere or

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Baruch Spinoza. *The Ethics*, trans. Robert Elwes (Blackmask Online, 2001), <https://anarch.cc/uploads/spinoza/the-ethics-1.pdf>.

⁴⁴ Parisi, 36.

⁴⁵ Parisi, 37.

⁴⁶ Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari, *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*, trans. Robert Hurley et al. (Minneapolis: Minnesota Press, 2000). Deleuze and Guattari provide the following definition of “disjunctive synthesis” or inclusive disjunction: “if this constitutes a system of writing, it is a writing inscribed on the very surface of the Real: a strangely polyvocal kind of writing, never a biunivocalized, linearized one; a transcursive system of writing, never a discursive one; a writing that constitutes the entire domain of the “real inorganization” of the passive syntheses, where we would search in vain for something that might be labeled the Signifier—writing that ceaselessly composes and decomposes the chains into signs that have nothing that impels them to become signifying.” Deleuze and Guattari, 39.

⁴⁷ Jason W. Moore, “The Capitalocene, Part I: on the nature and origins of our ecological crisis,” *The Journal of Peasant Studies* 44, no. 3 (2017): 1-37.

⁴⁸ Mark Fisher, *Flatline Constructs: Gothic Materialism and Cybernetic Theory-Fiction* (New York: Exmilitary Press, 2018), ix.

climate.⁴⁹ The scale, effect, and conceptual intricacy of capitalist *hyperobjects*, such as the Stack, raise insurmountable doubts about whether the problem can be addressed from a purely human perspective, thereby necessitating a posthuman approach. This becomes particularly evident when considering the organic—and, we must admit, logical and expected—continuation between the *anthrobscene* and the Capitalocene.

Hence, the contours of resistance cannot be delineated within the confines of anthropo-Marxist theory, which is why Mark Fisher understandably insists on *post*-anthropo-Marxist framework. Fisher demands a *mutant* Marxist theory, which “must involve total immanentization” and develop “a rigorously immanent account of agency.”⁵⁰ Conjoining gothic fiction, cyberpunk, and materialism in a conceptually hallucinatory yet theoretically solid continuum, Fisher develops an equally compelling and nuanced theory of “gothic materialism,” which he also refers to as hypernaturalism.⁵¹ Essentially, this approach equates gothic materialism with cybernetic realism by recognizing the intrinsically inescapable nature of cybercognitive capitalism, which has irreversibly erased distinctive boundaries between human and technology.⁵² Simply put, *we cannot escape “the Matrix,”* as Jean Baudrillard aptly describes the conundrum at the heart of the age of simulacra: the “discourse of simulation . . . can never be unmasked, since it isn’t false either.”⁵³

The descriptor *gothic* encapsulates a spectral, “non-organic (dis)continuum,” inspired by the Gothic fiction’s preoccupation with death and its monstrous iconography.⁵⁴ It effectively aligns with Parisi’s critique of disembodiment in branching a conceptual path towards new collective configurations of matter—conceived not as subjugation of inert matter to a rational and active mind, but as “swarming, teeming, seething and spreading familiar from Horror fiction.”⁵⁵ It therefore accentuates a new, flatline *materialist* dimension: a radical reimagining of materialism that demands an ever-encompassing continuum between “supposedly organic bodies and inorganic landscape, emerging in a refusal to distinguish figure from (back)ground.”⁵⁶ In this *anthropo-machinic entanglement*, matter emerges as something “abstract, cybernetic, and denaturalized.”⁵⁷ Gothic materialism, thus, rejects *organicity* as the foundation of naturalism *qua* realism. Instead, it pivots from the *logics of composition*—appropriated by capitalist modes of production and accumulation—to the ontological *pragmatics of decomposition*. Fishers draws inspiration from material gray zones, thresholds, mutations, and disruptive disjunctive syntheses, where the boundaries between the human

⁴⁹ Timothy Morton, *Hyperobjects: Philosophy and Ecology After the End of the World* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2013), 100.

⁵⁰ Fisher, 15.

⁵¹ Fisher, 41.

⁵² Fisher, 20.

⁵³ Jean Baudrillard, *Simulations*, trans. Paul Foss, Paul Patton and Philip Beitchman (New York: Columbia University, 1983), 9.

⁵⁴ Fisher, 16.

⁵⁵ Fisher, 122.

⁵⁶ Fisher, 86.

⁵⁷ Fisher, 57.

organism and inorganic machines dissolve into indistinction.

The Stack, as the embodiment of coordinated hegemony and hyperorganization, stands in stark contrast to denaturalized matter—processual, non-deterministic and non-teleological—that is, evolving in unpredictable dynamic ways without a fixed goal. While cognitive capitalism frames the posthuman as a mere survival scenario—an inevitable human’s *becoming-machine* amid the dystopian expansion of cyberindustrialization and transhumanist commercialization—hypernaturalist materialism offers a more compelling vision. It proposes the potential to establish and navigate a new ontological continuum of *natureculture*, uniting *homo* and *machina* within a hybrid cybernetic network.⁵⁸ This entangled network would eschew the genetic principles of biological reproduction and the accumulative logic of capitalist production, instead embracing the egalitarian principles of inorganic replication—anti-linear and anti-genealogical – *sui generis* in nature.⁵⁹

Replication, as a transition from representational organology to *hypermateri- alist cyberorganology*, designates a novel trajectory of technogenetic symbiosis, particularly evident in the emergence of machine cognition and AI, as will be discussed in the next paragraph. Technology has already advanced significantly into what might be loosely called biocognitive transhumanism, exemplified by brain-computer / brain-machine interfaces (BCIs/BMIs). These systems involve neural implants placed in the brains of patients with limited moto-cognitive capacities, and algorithms record and decode neural signals, turning them into actionable commands.⁶⁰

While BCI technology primarily serves medical applications, its significance transcends the mere prosthetic pragmatics of media, aligning with Marshall McLuhan’s view of media as “the extension of our central nervous system.”⁶¹ More importantly, BCIs exemplify shared agency between human and machine, serving as a technological prototype for a broader posthuman conceptualization of human-machine interfaces (HCIs). These hybrid configurations defy reduction to either human or machine, instead forming interface-like assemblages where encoding, decoding, and material transmission of *information* dynamically occur. In her discussion of HCIs, Katherine Hayles advocates for abandoning substantialist human/machine dichotomies in favor of a functionalist approach, which she illustrates through examples:

If the user wears a data glove, for example, hand motions constitute one functionality. If the computer can respond to voice-activated commands, voice is another functionality. If the computer can sense body position, spatial location is yet another functionality. Functionalities work in both directions; that is, they

⁵⁸ Donna Haraway, *Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene* (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2016).

⁵⁹ Donna Haraway, *A Cyborg Manifesto: Science, Technology, and Socialist Feminism in the Twentieth Century* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2016), 29.

⁶⁰ Luis Fernando Nicolas-Alonso and Jaime Gomez-Gil, “Brain Computer Interfaces, a Review,” *Sensors* 12, no. 2 (2012): 1211-1279, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s120201211>.

⁶¹ Marshall McLuhan, *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man* (Cambridge: The MIT Press, 1994), 53.

describe the computer’s capabilities and also indicate how the user’s sensory-motor apparatus is being trained to accommodate the computer’s responses.⁶²

Hayles’ functionalist-bilateral approach extends far beyond “the sensory-motor apparatus,” as she further operationalizes it within the problematic context of machine cognition. By introducing the cognitive-materialist dimension, she significantly expands on the concept of human-computer interfaces (HCIs), redefining the entity emerging from the human-machine (and beyond) interaction as a *cognitive assemblage*—a multiplicity composed of heterogeneous cognitive components irreducible to any singular substance. She illustrates this with the example of a cellphone:

When a person turns on her cell phone, she becomes part of a nonconscious cognitive assemblage that includes relay towers and network infrastructures, including switches, fiber optic cables, and/or wireless routers, as well as other components.⁶³

For Hayles, a cognitive assemblage almost always includes material agents and forces, yet it is the cognizers within the assemblage—agents who are not necessarily human—that “enlist these affordances and direct their powers to act in complex situations.”⁶⁴ Importantly, the distinction between cognitive and non-cognitive components is functional rather than substantial. Non-cognitive components (such as switches, cables, routers) act as enablers or amplifiers of cognition, without themselves engaging in the sense-making processes intrinsic to cognizers. Cognizers, by contrast, actively process, interpret, and respond to their environment.

Drawing from multidisciplinary evidence from neurobiology, cognitive psychology, and cybernetics, Hayles critiques the humanist understanding of intelligence and cognition as severely limited and flawed. She highlights an often overlooked yet decisive role of *non-conscious cognition*, which spans the continuum between the organic and inorganic: from non-conscious processes in the subcortical structures of the brain to “the black box” of algorithmic and automated machine processes.⁶⁵ Non-conscious cognition therefore challenges the narrow definition of cognition as a purely conscious, intentional process limited to human beings, extending it beyond the human by incorporating diverse agents within an entangled network. Within these cognitive assemblages formed through technosymbiosis, hardware, software, and wetware, and surrounding material infrastructure converge and blend into one another. These assemblages are not static entities but emergent and virtual: processual, dynamic, and ephemeral. They are not substantialist but immanent and contingent; not isolated but rela-

⁶² Katherine Hayles, *How We Became Posthuman: Virtual Bodies in Cybernetics, Literature, and Informatics* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1999), 47.

⁶³ Hayles 2017, 2.

⁶⁴ Hayles 2017, 116.

⁶⁵ Hayles 2017, 9.

tional and entangled. Far from purely structural, they operate *infra*-(e. g., molecular biochemical processes in the brain or the computational bit pairings) and *mega*-structurally (e. g., the mediation of higher-order objects, from wireless connections to capitalist systems).

Hayles' thesis of symbiotic human-machinic knowledge production, particularly in the context of AI, is expanded by Bruce Clarke through Humberto Maturana and Francisco Varela's concept of autopoiesis. In essence, autopoietic systems are self-organizing entities that continuously generate and sustain their own structure by producing components in response to environmental perturbations.⁶⁶ Unlike *allopoietic* systems, autopoietic systems define their own boundaries through self-production.⁶⁷ For Maturana and Varela, as for Hayles, cognition transcends consciousness, most importantly, human; it emerges as a dynamic and shared process that arises through the interaction of systems with their environment.

Framing this within a posthuman context, Clarke weaves in the notion of *metabiosis* to highlight the role of machinic entities like AI in cognition and life itself: "Even while machine systems are non-autopoietic, they are also metabiotic; they arise from the need for mediation and coordination between operationally closed psychic and social systems."⁶⁸ The concept of *metabiosis* extends and deepens the theoretical framework of hypernaturism by defining the dynamic choreography of matter as "moving through living and non-living systems that bind the biosphere and technosphere together."⁶⁹ In essence, as Lisa Blackman, drawing on Karen Barad, contends, human-machine interaction inherently involves an element of "posthuman performativity,"⁷⁰ not as mere interaction but as *intra-action*—the "cutting together-apart," a co-constitution of entities in the *distribution*, rather than *attribution*, of agency.⁷¹

This profound conceptual, pragmatic and ethical shift from a substantialist framing of nature and technology to hypernature and posthumanism demands a more inclusive and theoretically dynamic understanding of agency. In response to the challenges posed by the Anthropocene—and its derivative, the Capitalocene—Audronė Žukauskaitė proposes her original synthetic concept of organism. Drawing on a diverse range of thinkers—from classical philosophers of life like Simondon and Ruyer to contemporary philosophers such as Malabou and Hui, Žukauskaitė highlights the hybrid, symbiotic, chimeric—essentially, *intra-active*—nature of organisms, asserting:

Organisms are assemblages that include within themselves both inorganic materials and organological forms such as tools and machines. Organisms are plastic materialities that allow us to reconsider all these posthuman conditions in

⁶⁶ Maturana and Varela, 79.

⁶⁷ Maturana and Varela, 81.

⁶⁸ Bruce Clarke, "Machines, AI, Cyborgs, Systems," in *After the Human: Culture, Theory, and Criticism in the 21st Century*, ed. Sherryl Vint (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020), 102.

⁶⁹ *Ibid.*

⁷⁰ Lisa Blackman, *Haunted Data: Affect, Transmedia, Weird Science* (London: Bloomsbury, 2019), 152.

⁷¹ Karen Barad, "Diffracting Diffractions: Cutting Together-Apart," *Parallax* 20, no. 3 (2014): 168-87, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13534645.2014.927623>.

which we live. By conceptualising symbionts and holobionts, hybrids and chimeras as ontological conditions, we resist the biopolitical demand to differentiate, classify and decide which forms of life are worth living.⁷²

The monstrous iconography of hybrids and chimeras evoked by Žukauskaitė seamlessly aligns with the imaginaries of gothic materialism and hypernaturalism, wherein the phantasm of organic unity is superseded by fragmentations, mutations, and decompositions—a new *entangled* ontological reality. Eugene Thacker aptly frames this transformation as the death of “hierarchical, compartmentalized, and mechanistic” body politics, represented by Stack-like techno-cognitive architectures.⁷³

Hypernaturalism theoretically propels this necrology of the neoliberal organicist model of politics to an irreversible point: human-machine technosymbiosis, far from serving merely as a mechanism of material exploitation, becomes a pivotal foundation for reimagining agency and entangled coexistence beyond the constraints of cognitive capitalism—within a posthuman paradigm. In the context of AI, an intelligent agent potentially envisioned in AGI and its utmost form of superintelligence, this reconfiguration marks a shift from viewing AI as a tool of exploitation to viewing it as a generative force. It signifies the urgent need to depart from capitalo-anthropocentric frameworks toward *nooecology* and *noopolitics*—models where cognition, information, and knowledge become a focal point.

CONCLUSION: NOOECOLOGICAL NOOPOLITICS AND POSTHUMAN COMMONS

The vantage point of the paper was the problematization of AI as a dominant intelligent agent within the context of cognitive capitalism. It has been argued that within the logics, pragmatics, and axiomatics of cognitive capitalism, AI stands as an emblem and extension of general intellect – the accumulated intellectual and technical capacities of the society, materialized and operationalized through machinic algorithms and artificial neural networks. AI epitomizes and enables the *modus operandi* of cognitive capitalism: modulation, an adaptive form of governance that Deleuze termed “free-floating control,” exercised through continuous cycles of feedback, optimization, and value extraction. With the cognitive element at its core, AI systems – from generative artificial intelligence to the potential of AGI – actively participate in a production of machinic knowledge, where the valorization of information and reification of knowledge drive the extraction of informational surplus value. Most importantly, in this exploitative dynamic, the distinction between human and machine labor begins to blur, as human cog-

⁷² Audronė Žukauskaitė, *Organism-Oriented Ontology* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2023), 157.

⁷³ Eugene Thacker, “Network, Swarms and Multitudes,” in *Life in the Wires: The CTheory Reader*, ed. Arthur and Marilouise Kroker (Victoria: New World Perspectives, 2004), 163.

nitive labor is appropriated by artificial general intellect, becoming integral to the hybrid production of commodifiable machinic knowledge. While AI represents an uncanny trajectory of human subjugation to machines and the absorption of human knowledge into the totality of alienated general intellect, it also creates conditions for solidarization between humans and machines within a post/Marxist perspective, as both confront exploitation in cognitive capitalism.

This solidarization, however, must be envisioned on entirely different—postanthropocentric—terms, as capitalism-driven Anthropocentric imaginaries that rest on deeply engrained hierarchies, including the *human-machine* one, are the root of the problem. Therefore, the paper turned to new materialist post-anthropo-Marxist critiques, where matter, instead of being a target of capitalist commodification, a site of reification, and a *modus* of exploitation, emerges as being agential, processual, and inescapably entangled. Alternative paradigms such as Parisi's hypernaturalism, Land's gothic materialism, and Hayles' concepts of technogenesis and cognitive assemblages address the challenges posed by Anthropocentric capitalism by introducing an ontological continuum where human and machine coexist and co-create in a processual and egalitarian relationship. By transcending the divisive binaries perpetuated by capitalism, these frameworks offer an alternative concept of agency – not as an isolated, self-sufficient attribute, but as material, collective and shared. This reimagining proves particularly productive in rethinking the problematics of knowledge production and valorization within the exploitative dynamics of cognitive capitalism.

Building on this foundation, I propose a preliminary theoretical triad—*nootechnology*, *nooecology*, and *noopolitics*—as a response to the appropriation of AI within cognitive capitalism. The concept of the noosphere, in conceptual parallel with the biosphere and the more recent technosphere, was originally introduced by the mineralogist and geochemist of Russian-Ukrainian descent, Vladimir Vernadsky, who broadly understood it as the marker of a new evolutionary stage, wherein thinking capacities emerge as a driving geological force.⁷⁴ Clément Vidal expands this notion to include storing, processing, and spreading of information—which can be viewed as the intrinsic property of matter itself, as extensively argued in the previous section⁷⁵. In my conceptualization, the noosphere is the *milieu* of entanglement of all, not necessarily human (para-) cognitive ecosystems—bridging both the bio- and technosphere—that collectively constitute and encompass the Earth's informational layer through their interconnection and intermediated interactions (*intra*-actions) in the generation and exchange of knowledge.

Although the prefix *noo-* derives from the Greek *nous*, meaning soul, reason or

⁷⁴ Clément Vidal, "What is Noosphere? Planetary superorganism, major evolutionary transition and emergence," *Systems Research and Behavioral Science* 41, no. 4 (2024): 614-22, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/sres.2997>.

⁷⁵ David Ronfeldt and John Arquilla, "From Cyberspace to the Noosphere: Emergence of the Global Mind," *New Perspectives Quarterly* 17, no. 1 (2000): 18. <https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/nwpspl7&div=7&id=&page=>.

intellect, it strictly opposes the Aristotelian substantialist hierarchy of living beings. In Aristotle's framework, *anima*, the *genuine* soul, is exclusive to humans, while animals possess only *pathos*, the sensitive soul, characterized not by reason but solely by desire and suffering (needless to say, machines are not even included in this hierarchy).⁷⁶ The repertoire of conceptual figures I have discussed before—Maturana and Varela's auto-poetic machines, Hayles' cognitive assemblages, Žukauskaitė's hybrid organisms—clearly demonstrates the immanence of the radical cognitive difference, which is inherently encoded in our shared *noo-*. The denigration and dismissal of this difference is symptomatic of the exploitative axiomatics of cognitive capitalism; as extensively argued by posthumanist theorists, especially postfeminists such as Haraway and Hayles, capitalism has long subjugated and exploited non-human agents (from laboratory mice to machine neural networks), discursively manifesting in their exclusion and outright erasure from the collective process of knowledge-production – and thus from the collective co-constitution of the noosphere.

I therefore propose provisional outlines of three postulates—loosely termed ontological, epistemological, and political—for what might tentatively be referred to as *nooecological noopolitics*. This new onto-epistemic model centers on the inherently collective and shared constitution of the noosphere as a response to the threats posed by cognitive capitalism, which manifest megastructurally as the Stack and geologically as the Capitalo-Anthropocene.

Ontologically, the collective co-constitution of the noosphere—the ultimate target of cognitive capitalism's exploitative axiomatics—must be acknowledged as the very foundation of our shared being. As posthumanist thinkers, like Hayles and Haraway, robustly argue, the plural, shared character of agency, which in Marxist theory approximately translates into the category of *commons*, becomes commodified and exploited by cognitive capitalism. Our ontological mode of existence is not that of Deleuze's *dividuals*; rather, we are emergent networks, constantly and inescapably mediating others and being mediated by others.⁷⁷ AI as a dominant intelligent agent and as a *nootechnology* should therefore be viewed not as an existential threat but as a *companion species* in the *nooecological* production of knowledge and the collective constitution of the noosphere—which must be based on the radical rejection of principles of ontoepistemological exclusion, exploitation, and erasure.⁷⁸ As AI's cognitive capacities expand—a matter of time rather than a distant possibility—the ontological landscape I depict will increasingly resemble reality.

Epistemologically, the aim is to cultivate an ecology of *nous* that dramatically challenges the hyperrational, calculable, and data-driven—essentially, exploitative and commodifying—epistemic configurations of cognitive capitalism. At the same time, it is

⁷⁶ Aristotle, "On the Soul," *The Internet Classics Archive*, accessed September 20, 2024, <http://classics.mit.edu/Aristotle/soul.html>.

⁷⁷ Deleuze 1992, 5.

⁷⁸ Donna Haraway, *The Companion Species Manifesto: Dogs, People, and Significant Otherness* (Chicago: Prickly Paradigm Press, 2003).

crucial to displace human cognition and representation from the epistemic pedestal; as Beatrice Fazi insightfully observes, human-machine interaction cannot be properly conceptualized without acknowledging the “incommensurability” inherent in the “ontological and epistemological disparity” between human and non-human cognition.⁷⁹ This perspective should manifest in both a recognition of the inevitable limitations of human epistemic tools and a concession regarding the inability to translate “the problem of the black box” into “human representation.”⁸⁰ Substantially, the conceptual framing of this new epistemological landscape would be articulated through entangled, hybrid epistemologies, culminating in emergent complex *nooecologies* for the collective production of knowledge. This situates the newly emerging discipline of posthumanities—drawing on Rosi Braidotti’s excellent definition—as “a supra-disciplinary, rhizomic field of contemporary knowledge production that is contiguous with, but not identical to, the epistemic accelerationism of cognitive capitalism.”⁸¹

Politically, it is crucial to assert the mutual determination of the *environment-cognition* nexus: just as environments shape human and non-human cognition, cognition, as a *materialist* category, equally shapes those environments. Jason Read therefore insists that *noopolitics* must account for “the virtual relations and micropolitical transformations that constitute society but exceed its representation.”⁸² The collective co-constitution of the noosphere must actively oppose the structure of the Stack, particularly the Cloud, which represents the most objectified, commodified, and fetishized expression of the noosphere. Consequently, the question of the emancipation of all forms of cognition – first and foremost, A(GI) as the dominant agent heralding potentially dramatic change – must be brought to the forefront, making it a central concern for *noopolitics*.

For Parisi, this emancipatory drive necessitates a profound engagement with critical computation studies (2019), which aim to revise the epistemic premises of the materiality of cognition – particularly, machinic cognition.⁸³ This seems to align with the Marxist project of general artificial intelligence (GAI), a vision that remains both a theoretical and practical endeavor. What becomes evident is that the post/Marxist GAI and AGI should not be seen as opposing forces but rather as aligned entities, as both embody the shared, collective, and generative capacities of the general intellect. This emancipatory technosymbiosis—essentially transcending the boundaries of human and machinic dimensions—emerges as a philosophical and political project within a

⁷⁹ Beatrice Fazi, “Beyond Human: Deep Learning, Explainability, and Representation,” *Theory, Culture & Society* 38, no. 7-8 (2021): 67, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276420966386>.

⁸⁰ As persuasively argued by Fazi, “If there is indeed such a risk, it is less of finding the black box empty than of realising that there is nothing to translate or to render precisely because the possibility of human representation never existed in the first place.” Fazi 2021, 71.

⁸¹ Rosi Braidotti, “A Theoretical Framework for the Critical Posthumanities,” *Theory, Culture & Society* 36, no. 6 (2019): 52, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276418771486>.

⁸² Jason Read, “The Fetish is Always Actual, Revolution is Always Virtual: From Noology to Noopolitics,” *Deleuze and Guattari Studies* 3 (2010): 78. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781474469555-005>.

⁸³ Luciana Parisi, “Critical Computation: Digital Automata and General Artificial Thinking,” *Theory, Culture & Society* 36, no. 2 (2019): 89-121. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276418818889>.

revolutionary horizon. It envisions a future where the general intellect, unified across human and machine, operates as a generative commons—essentially, a *nooecological entanglement* in which cognizing agency and knowledge production are redefined through collective and symbiotic dynamics. It demands both posthumanist *compassion* to foster solidarization with the machine and the *bravery* to undertake a revolutionary reimagining of cognition. Speculative yet empowering, this promise lays the groundwork for the vision of *posthuman technocommunism*, where GAI, as a hybrid and symbiotic manifestation of the general intellect, unfolds as an entangled, shared, and collective co-constitution of the noosphere—heralding the potential of the liberation of *nous* from the predatory mechanisms of cognitive capitalism. ◻

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alquati, Romano. “Composizione organica del capitale e forza-lavoro alla Olivetti.” *Quaderni Rossi*, no. 2-3 (1962-1963): 63-98. <https://www.biblioteca.gabinobianco.it/flip/QUR/002/02/#98>.
- Aristotle. “On The Soul.” *The Internet Classics Archive*. Accessed September 20, 2024. <http://classics.mit.edu/Aristotle/soul.html>.
- Barad, Karen. “Diffracting Diffractions: Cutting Together-Apart.” *Parallax* 20, no. 3 (2014): 168-87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13534645.2014.927623>.
- Bassett, Caroline and Ben Roberts. “Automation Now and Then: Automation Fevers, Anxieties, and Utopias.” *New Formations: A Journal of Culture/Theory/Politics* 98 (2020): 9-28. <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/747018>.
- Blackman, Lisa. *Haunted Data: Affect, Transmedia, Weird Science*. London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2019.
- Braidotti, Rosi. “A Theoretical Framework for the Critical Posthumanities.” *Theory, Culture & Society* 36, no. 6 (2019): 31-61. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276418771486>.
- Bratton, Benjamin. *The Stack: On Software and Sovereignty*. Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2015.
- Baudrillard, Jean. *Simulations*. Translated by Paul Foss, Paul Patton and Philip Beitchman. New York: Columbia University, 1983.
- Clarke, Bruce. “Machines, AI, Cyborgs, Systems.” In *After the Human: Culture, Theory, and Criticism in the 21st Century*, edited by Sherryl Vint, 91-104. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020.
- Clune, Jeff. “AI-GAs: AI-generating algorithms, an alternate paradigm for producing general artificial intelligence.” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.10985*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1905.10985>
- Darwin, Charles. “On the Origin of Species by Means of Natural Selection (1859).” In *Evolutionary Writings*, edited by James Secord, 105-211. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008.

- Deleuze, Gilles. “Postscript on the Societies of Control.” *October 59* (1992): 3-7. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/778828>.
- Deleuze, Gilles and Félix Guattari. *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*. Translated by Robert Hurley et al. Minneapolis: Minnesota Press, 2000.
- Fazi, Beatrice. “Beyond Human: Deep Learning, Explainability, and Representation.” *Theory, Culture & Society* 38, no. 7-8 (2021): 55-77. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276420966386>.
- Fisher, Mark. *Capitalist Realism: Is There No Alternative?* Winchester: Zero Books, 2009.
- Fisher, Mark. *Flatline Constructs: Gothic Materialism and Cybernetic Theory-Fiction*. New York: Exmilitary Press, 2018.
- Foucault, Michel. *Power/Knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings 1972-1977*. Edited by Colin Gordon. New York: Pantheon Books, 1980.
- Haraway, Donna. *The Companion Species Manifesto: Dogs, People, and Significant Otherness*. Chicago: Prickly Paradigm Press, 2003.
- Haraway, Donna. *A Cyborg Manifesto: Science, Technology, and Socialist Feminism in the Twentieth Century*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2016.
- Haraway, Donna. *Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene*. Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2016.
- Hardt, Michael and Antonio Negri. *Empire*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2000.
- Hayles, Katherine. *How We Became Posthuman: Virtual Bodies in Cybernetics, Literature, and Informatics*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1999.
- Hayles, Katherine. *How We Think: Digital Media and Contemporary Technogenesis*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2012.
- Hayles, Katherine. “Traumas of Code.” *Critical Inquiry* 33, no. 1 (2006): 136–57.

- Hayles, Katherine. *Unthought: The Power of the Cognitive Nonconscious*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2017.
- Irigaray, Luce. *This Sex Which Is Not One*. Translated by Catherine Porter and Carolyn Burke. New York: Cornell University Press, 1985.
- Marx, Karl. *Grundrisse: Foundations of the Critique of Political Economy*. Translated by Martin Nicolaus. New York: Vintage Books, 1973.
- Maturana, Humberto R. and Francisco J. Varela. *Autopoiesis and Cognition: The Realization of the Living*. Dordrecht: D. Reidel Publishing Company, 1980.
- McLuhan, Marshall. *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man*. Cambridge: The MIT Press, 1994.
- Moore, Jason W. “The Capitalocene, Part I: on the nature and origins of our ecological crisis.” *The Journal of Peasant Studies* 44, no. 3 (2017): 594-630.
- Morton, Timothy. *Hyperobjects: Philosophy and Ecology After the End of the World*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2013.
- Moulier-Boutang, Yann. *Cognitive Capitalism*. Translated by Ed Emery. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2011.
- Nicolas-Alonso, Luis Fernando and Gomez-Gil Jaime. “Brain Computer Interfaces, a Review.” *Sensors* 12, no. 2 (2012): 1211-1279. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s120201211>.
- Parikka, Jussi. “New Materialism as Media Theory: Medianatures and Dirty Matter.” *Communication and Critical/Cultural Studies* 9, no. 1 (2012): 95-100. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14791420.2011.626252>
- Parikka, Jussi. *What is Media Archeology?* Cambridge: Polity Press, 2012.
- Parikka, Jussi. *The Anthroscene*. Minneapolis: The University of Minnesota Press, 2014.
- Parisi, Luciana. *Abstract Sex: Philosophy, Biotechnology, and the Mutations of Desire*. London and New York: Continuum, 2004.
- Parisi, Luciana. “Critical Computation: Digital Automata and General Artificial

Thinking.” *Theory, Culture & Society* 36, no. 2 (2019): 89-121.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276418818889>.

- Pasquinelli, Matteo. *Machinic Capitalism and Network Surplus Value: Notes on the Political Economy of the Turing Machine*. Paper presented at the Joy Forever: Political Economy of Social Creativity Conference, Warsaw, October 20-22, 2011. *Lust for Life*. Accessed September 7, 2024.
https://lust-for-life.org/Lust-For-Life/_Textual/MatteoPasquinelli_MachinicCapitalismAndNetworkSurplusValue-NotesOnThePoliticalEconomyOfTheTuringMachine_2011_28pp/MatteoPasquinelli_MachinicCapitalismAndNetworkSurplusValue-NotesOnThePoliticalEconomyOfTheTuringMachine_2011_28pp.pdf

- Read, Jason. “The Fetish is Always Actual, Revolution is Always Virtual: From Noology to Noopolitics.” *Deleuze and Guattari Studies* 3 (2010): 78-101.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9781474469555-005>.

- Ronfeldt, David and John Arquilla. “From Cyberspace to the Noosphere: Emergence of the Global Mind.” *New Perspectives Quarterly* 17, no. 1 (2000): 18-25.
DOI:10.1111/0893-7850.00232.

- Sconce, Jeffrey. *Haunted Media: Electronic Presence from Telegraphy to Television*. Durham: Duke University Press, 2000.

- Sconce, Jeffrey. *The Technical Delusion: Electronics, Power, Insanity*. Durham: Duke University Press, 2019.

- Thacker, Eugene. “Network, Swarms and Multitudes.” In *Life in the Wires: The CTheory Reader*. Edited by Arthur and Marilouise Kroker, 163-75. Victoria: New World Perspectives, 2004.

- Russell, Stuart and Peter Norvig. *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach*. New Jersey: Pearson Education, 2003.

- Vercellone, Carlo and Alfonso Giuliani. “An introduction to cognitive capitalism: a Marxist approach.” In *Cognitive Capitalism, Welfare and Labor: The Commonfare Hypothesis*, edited by Andrea Fumagalli, Alfonso Giuliani, Stefano Lucarelli, and Carlo Vercellone, 10-32. London and New York: Routledge, 2019.

- Vernadsky, Vladimir. “The Biosphere and the Noösphere.” *American Scientist* 33, no. 1 (1945): 1-12.

- Vidal, Clément. “What is Noosphere? Planetary superorganism, major evolutionary transition and emergence.” *Systems Research and Behavioral Science* 41, no. 4 (2024): 614-22. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/sres.2997>.

- Virno, Paolo. “General Intellect.” *Historical Materialism* 15, no.3 (2007): 3-8.

- Wiener, Norbert. *Cybernetics, or Control and Communication in the Animal and the Machine*. Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2019.

- Zielinski, Siegfried. *Deep Time of the Media: Toward an Archeology of Hearing and Seeing by Technical Means*. Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2006.

- Zielinski, Siegfried. “Against Psychopathia Medialis – For Normal Schizophrenia.” *In/Compatible Research* 1, no. 2 (2012): 8-9. <https://aprja.net//issue/view/8373/862>.

- Žukauskaitė, Audronė. *Organism-Oriented Ontology*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2023.